

NASA Airborne and Field Data Workshop (2024)

Summary and Findings

Report Authors:

Lindsay Parker, ESDIS/SSAI

Megan Buzanowicz, ADNET/ASDC

Stephanie Wingo, UAH/NASA IMPACT/ADMG

Workshop Organizing Committee:

Sara Lubkin, NASA ESDIS

Michele Thornton, ORNL DAAC

Bruce Wilson, ORNL DAAC

Megan Buzanowicz, ADNET/ASDC

Yaxing Wei, ORNL DAAC

Stephanie Wingo, UAH/NASA IMPACT/ADMG

Katherine Saad, NASA ESDS/NASA HQ

Executive Summary

For decades, NASA has conducted field campaigns for the collection of airborne and field observations. These investigations cover a wide range of measurements from passive remote sensing (multi-spectral, hyperspectral) to active remote sensing (laser altimeters, synthetic aperture radar), in-situ atmospheric chemistry and composition, and ground-based remote sensing (e.g., lidar) to ground-based in-situ measurements. The data are archived and distributed by NASA's Earth Science Data and Information Systems (ESDIS) and the Distributed Active Archive Centers (DAACs) working closely with the science teams. Field campaigns help to propel advances in the Earth sciences by providing a deeper understanding of specific processes and phenomena as well as improve the accuracy of and deepen trust in NASA's satellite measurements. As a follow-on and recommendation from the 2022 Airborne and Field Data Workshop, members of NASA's Earth Science Data Systems (ESDS), the Airborne Data Management Group (ADMG), ESDIS, and several DAACs co-organized and hosted a second two-day Airborne and Field Data Workshop from 23-24 April 2024. The goals of the virtual workshop were to provide updates on changes that have been implemented by ESDIS, ADMG, and the DAACs based on feedback at and since the 2022 workshop and to continue identifying ways to enhance the findability, accessibility, and usability of suborbital data. More than 80 participants were encouraged through multiple opportunities to provide feedback on the primary issues affecting NASA suborbital data. The feedback gathered during the workshop was sorted into categories and actionable items for review and recommendation by the Airborne and Field Data Working Group (AFDWG) and continues to be discussed openly by the group. Key areas noted for continued focus include: simplifying access points and streamlining tools and services;

improved conventions and consistency for metadata, standards, and implementation; advancing visualization capacity; expanded communication avenues; and continued development of new efficiencies for open science and programmatic aspects.

Introduction

The NASA Earth Science Data Systems (ESDS) Airborne and Field Data Working Group (AFDWG) is an active collaboration between NASA's Airborne Data Management Group (ADMG) within the agency's Interagency Implementation and Advanced Concepts Team (IMPACT) Project, leadership from the Earth Science Data and Information System (ESDIS) Project, and staff from various Distributed Active Archive Centers (DAACs) with significant airborne and field data holdings and engagement. The AFDWG meets monthly to facilitate advanced data stewardship discussions; highlight concerns among communities of data producers, stewards, and users; and deliver actionable recommendations to improve the discoverability, accessibility, and (re)usability of NASA's airborne and field data. In the spring of 2022, the AFDWG held its [first NASA Airborne and Field Data Workshop](#), and released [a summary report](#) with recommended actions based on participant feedback.

This report highlights accomplishments since the 2022 Workshop, describes motivations for the second workshop, details the 2024 event agenda, provides participant metrics, explains how attendees' inputs were analyzed and synthesized, and presents recommendations for continued and new actions.

In the context of ongoing activities and developments in response to the 2022 workshop, the AFDWG determined a second workshop would be beneficial to provide an update on the implementation of recommendations from the first workshop and gather new feedback. A second two-day, fully virtual workshop was held 23-24 April 2024. Goals for the 2024 workshop included discussion of ADMG and DAAC activities resulting from the first workshop, updates on evolving best practices and processes for suborbital NASA data, as well as stakeholder-driven discussions on needs for future directions.

Summary of Accomplishments from 2022 Workshop

The AFDWG planned and hosted the first Airborne and Field Data Workshop virtually in March 2022. The goals of the 2022 workshop were to gather feedback from data users and data producers to improve the acquisition and use of NASA's airborne and field data; identify new ways to improve data discovery, access, and reuse; and to consider ways of more fully realizing the value of suborbital data for scientific gains within an open-source framework.

Feedback from 2022 was sorted into twelve categories: Data and Information Access, Communication, Consistency, Merged or Higher-Level Data, Metadata, Open-Source Science, Cloud, Programmatic Change, Quality, Search and Discovery, Support, and Tools. Tools,

Communication, Consistency, and Data Access received the most interest. The prioritized set of recommendations from the 2022 workshop were:

1. *Assign DAACs to campaigns as soon as possible after the award.*
2. *Develop an Airborne and Field Data Resource Center (AFDRC) on Earthdata.*
3. *Improve DAAC Campaign, Instrument, Flight, and Event Information.*
4. *Make modifications to NASA's CMR to enhance field and airborne discoverability.*
5. *Improve search capabilities and ensure all airborne and field data can be found in Earthdata.*
6. Improve usability and interoperability of disparate data formats.
7. *Address inconsistent DAAC user experiences for both data users and data producers.*
8. Expand and improve an FCX-type tool.
9. Address large airborne and field file needs.
 - a. Provide the ability to subset large data.
 - b. Provide cloud-optimized data products.
10. *Provide the ability to search for multiple variables in the same data product.*
11. Identify and resolve intercloud data transfer issues.
12. Increase compatibility and coordination across other US agencies.

Note: Updates on efforts directly stemming from the italicized items were a major point of discussion in Sessions 2 and 3.

Information about workshop outcomes has been openly provided and is publicly available. The [2022 workshop web page](#) continues to serve as a community resource with access to the workshop recordings and final report.

[NASA's Airborne and Field Data Resource Center \(AFDRC\)](#) debuted in late 2023 in direct response to the 2022 Workshop Recommendations. The AFDRC consolidates information and resources to help data users discover information about NASA's airborne and field campaign measurements and instruments; provide tools and services to help find, access, visualize and work with airborne and field data; and point towards various learning resources. Information is provided for data producers who may be interested in submitting their airborne and field data for archival and distribution by a DAAC. Sections within the AFDRC provide information and links for users to learn about data, find and access data, use data, archive data, as well as help/glossary/acronyms lists. DAACs are able to continually submit new resources to be included in the AFDRC.

2024 Workshop Description

The 2024 workshop drew over 135 registrants with 89 attendees on Day 1 and 79 attendees on Day 2. Attendees included data users, data producers, those who consider themselves both data users and producers, as well as personnel from various DAACs, NASA Headquarters, ADMG, and ESDIS (Appendix B). Attendees represented a wide range of scientific communities, including Applied Sciences, Terrestrial Ecology, Cryosphere, Atmospheric Science, Natural Disasters, Modeling, Science Policy, Interdisciplinary, Physical Oceanography, Ocean Biology,

Freshwater Systems, Crustal Dynamics, and Private Sector Use. Roughly 47% of attendees identified as students or early career researchers, and 27% identified as mid-career. The 2024 workshop drew an appropriate cohort to focus on recent improvements and continuing challenges for data discovery, findability, access and use.

Workshop Overview: Day 1

The workshop began with welcomes from Bruce Wilson (Oak Ridge National Laboratory DAAC Manager), Cerese Albers (NASA Earth Science Data Systems), and Matthew Fladeland (NASA Airborne Science Program).

Cerese Albers welcomed attendees with a walk through her early career experiences with NASA airborne hurricane observations, and with the SERVIR team on field observations for satellite-coincident land surface temperature observations to decision making for Kenyan farmers. She emphasized the importance of integrating students and interns, saying “NASA airborne and field observations really do launch a lot of people’s careers”. Her charge for the workshop was to consider how to further discovery, usability, and interoperability of NASA’s data, and prioritize FAIR and open principles, abiding by SPD-41a, for both data and software.

Matt Fladeland provided an overview of NASA’s Airborne Science Program (ASP), which operates out of NASA Ames Research Center. He described how the ASP supports investigations arising from the SMD’s six Earth Science focus areas (Atmospheric Composition, Weather and Atmospheric Dynamics, Climate Variability and Change, Water and Energy Cycle, Carbon Cycle and Ecosystems, and Earth Surface and Interior) using a variety of different instruments on board the agency’s fleet of research aircraft. These aircraft are fundamental support laboratories for the satellites on orbit as they are involved in every single aspect of the life cycle of satellite observations: from the development of a remote sensing technique, maturation of instruments, and calibration and validation work. NASA’s ASP continually develops new instruments to improve Earth observations and supports early career investigators through programs like the Student Airborne Research Program (SARP).

Session 1: Recap from 2022 Workshop & Goals for 2024

Megan Buzanowicz (Atmospheric Science Data Center (ASDC)) led Session 1 with a recap of the 2022 workshop. The goal of the first workshop was to gather feedback from data users and data producers to improve the discovery, access, and reuse of NASA’s airborne field data, with an emphasis on including input from the airborne community. Methods utilized to collect feedback during the workshop were highlighted, and the processes of evaluating the 2022 input were discussed. Feedback from the 2022 workshop was sorted into 12 categories: Data and Information Access, Communication, Consistency, Tools, Merged or Higher-Level Data,

Metadata, Open-Source Science, Cloud, Programmatic Change, Quality, Support, and Search and Discovery, with the first four receiving the most comments and feedback.

Stephanie Wingo (ADMG) then outlined the goals for the 2024 workshop:

- Providing progress updates on issues raised in 2022 by ADMG, ESDIS and DAAC representatives
- Community input for ongoing working group activities
- Discuss ongoing challenges and next opportunities – are there new items to add to the list of recommendations?
- Communicate what matters: documenting participants' input during discussions

A summary of responses to the 2024 workshop registration form questions (Appendix B) showed that many attendees were new to the workshop (i.e. they did not attend in 2022) but had worked with airborne and field data in the past. Workshop participants ranged from early-career scientists to senior scientists and are primarily data users. Broad representation was present in attendee disciplines, with a majority indicating their primary area of focus was applied science, followed by atmospheric science. Other feedback from the registration questionnaire was discussed including feedback about what is working well for data discovery, findability, access, and use, what is challenging, and what participants hope to gain from the workshop.

Session 1 concluded with a question & answer session moderated by Sara Lubkin (ESDIS) and Bruce Wilson (ORNL). Topics included webinars to teach students how to use the new website and how the feedback from the registration form was to be used.

Session 2: Recent NASA DAAC Activities

During Session 2 on Day 1, a sampling of NASA Data Distributed Active Archive Centers (DAACs) with airborne and field data holdings described their key activities since the 2022 workshop to address stewardship and data user concerns. Summaries of each presentation are provided in Table 1. Following these updates, an open discussion was held.

The ORNL DAAC is a comprehensive archive of terrestrial biogeochemistry and ecological dynamics observations and models.

The ASDC DAAC focuses on areas of radiation budget, clouds, aerosols, and tropospheric composition.

The Global Hydrometeorology Resource Center (GHRC) is NASA's hydrometeorology and lightning DAAC and supports a wide variety of airborne and field campaign missions relating to weather.

The Physical Oceanography DAAC (PO.DAAC) focuses on physical oceanography and terrestrial hydrology.

The National Snow and Ice Data Center (NSIDC) is NASA’s cryospheric DAAC supporting a mix of satellite missions, airborne campaigns, and field observations related to snow cover, sea ice, ice shelves, glaciers, frozen ground and more.

Table 1: Summary of Session 2 presentations on recent activities from subset of NASA DAACs with airborne and field data holdings

DAAC Representative	Recent Key Activities	Airborne and Field Relevance
<p>ORNL <i>Michele Thornton</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Assignments of key NAA Campaigns (SHIFT, BioSCape) that combine airborne and science data with concurrent field sampling. ● Close collaboration with JPL Science Team and AVIRIS instrument suite to standardize formats and cloud-native publication ● NASA Openscapes mentoring activities to address Earthdata cloud discovery, access, and analysis methods for airborne and field data ● Hosting of EcoSIS (Spectral Library) and EcoSML (Spectral Model Library) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Leveraging NASA Earthdata multi-file granule capabilities to improve AVIRIS-3 data products discovery in Earthdata Search and programmatically (CMR API) ● Creating geospatial files of attributed polygon representation of individual flight lines of Facility Instruments for use in GIS to provide visualization and query capabilities. Available as datasets. ● Collaborating with Science Teams to provide data in open and standardized file formats (ENVI -> netCDF) ● Tutorial development and workshop participation specific to field and airborne datasets (Annual Ecological Society of American, American Geophysical Union meetings)
<p>ASDC <i>Megan Buzanowicz</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Exploring suborbital preservation ● Archival and distribution of legacy suborbital data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Assisted with creation of Airborne and Field Data Resource Center ● Development of the Sub-Orbital Order Tool (SOOT) ● Earlier involvement with missions/science teams due to early DAAC assignment; participation in science team meetings <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Outreach materials ● Exploring adding suborbital data to Worldview to enhance data access
<p>GHRC <i>Geoffrey Stano</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Completing IMPACTS/CPEX archival; CPEX-AW and -CV are done ● Upcoming planning with the INCUS mission ● Using Openscapes community libraries to create jupyter notebook data recipes ● Updating Field Campaign Explorer (FCX) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Development and Implementation of Earthdata Pub <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Enterprise-level data producer interface ● ESDIS assigning DAACs earlier - See INCUS <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Opportunity to better coordinate with missions ● Utilizing NASA Openscapes for user services ● Development of the open-source Field Campaign Explorer (FCX) system ● Campaign landing pages for the whole collection
<p>PO.DAAC <i>Victoria McDonald</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Fully migrated to Earthdata Cloud ● Field campaigns delivering data directly to 	<p>New developments:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Metadata templates in development for common field data types (trajectory, profile, swath)

	<p>AWS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Exploring cloud-optimized formats (Zarr, COG) ● Exploring publishing airborne datasets as GIS map services through EGIS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Cloud-based Metadata Compliance Checker (coming soon!) <p>Pain points:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Integrating field data into PO.DAAC satellite tools & services (eg. SOTO, HiTIDE) ● Assigning field data processing levels ● Challenging for providers to upload large data to AWS
<p>NSIDC <i>Stephanie Wong</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Provided on-the-ground support for the final SnowEx field and airborne campaign in Alaska ● Added new LVIS observations to the IceBridge data portal ● Publishing ~3-4 new airborne/field data sets monthly ● Moving data to cloud 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Archiving DAAC for multiple field and airborne missions, including ASO, CLPX, IceBridge, LVIS, SMAPVEX, and SnowEx ● Produce tools and notebooks for visualizing and harmonizing airborne data from multiple campaigns/missions (e.g. IceBridge Portal and IceFlow) ● Provide on-the-ground data archival and collection support for both airborne and field campaigns (IceBridge, SMAPVEX, SnowEx) ● Hackweek support ● Regular engagement with mission/science teams

Notable points from the ensuing discussion, moderated by Deborah Smith (NASA IMPACT), are given below:

“How do the DAACs prioritize their work with respect to airborne and field data vs satellite data needs?”

- It depends and varies by DAAC priorities that are influenced by ESDIS.
- Getting feedback from this workshop will help us, DAAC’s, determine where to go.
- DAAC’s also leverage the user community to determine science priorities for example, TEMPO.

“Do DAAC’s share knowledge and technical developments with each other and if so, how? Can one expect a tool at one DAAC to be available someday at another?”

- The sharing of knowledge across DAAC’s is considerably better than years ago. Regarding Airborne and Field data, we engage with the workshops and the AFDWG. We are still trying to break down the boundaries to make tools work across DAAC’s.

“Will it be free for cloud-based services, e.g. getting data from the cloud?”

- Yes. Downloading data from the cloud will continue to be free.

“How about the data visualization and analysis in the cloud?”

- Yes in many cases. We are building/expanding tools that will run in the cloud, and access to those services will be free. Earthdata Cloud allows for access to data via native S3 protocols. Right now, accessing data via S3 requires the user to have their own cloud

accounts, which does have costs. NASA is providing for that in some of the completed programs -- grants are sometimes including budgets for cloud computing costs.

“Will the Lightning Dashboard at GHRC DAAC be further developed? Or will this become a candidate for deprecation as part of the ESDS tool de-duplication?”

- We do not think it will be deprecated. Please reach out to emphasize the use and importance of FCX.

“Do DAACs host notebooks for working with airborne and field data or is there a centralized location for accessing the code to use?”

- We host notebooks at different DAAC’s. Many of the DAAC’s collaborate through Openscapes. [Openscapes](#) provide platforms for DAAC’s to engage with each other and with science communities. It coordinates training materials development and organizes workshops, training, etc. Each DAAC has a specific focus domain, but there are a lot of synergies, regarding consistent data access, visualization, and analysis.
- There was a webinar that spoke to the Openscapes community based resources. Community Developed Resources, "[Explore the NASA Openscapes Earthdata Cloud Cookbook](#)"
- Openscapes has a lot of [great resources](#), even if you don't participate directly

“For all the DAAC’s - what are the issues with archiving airborne data versus issues with field data - how are these similar or different?”

- There is a lot of heterogeneity in airborne and field data and the DAAC’s are all working with the airborne teams to unify how they deliver data in a certain format, and with decent metadata, the same probably needs to be done at the field level.
- Both types of data typically go through the same process.
- We, DAAC’s, can work on the formats, names, etc and ensure consistency early with an early engagement with science teams.
- Airborne and Field usually go together to support science objectives. How DAAC’s support the discovery/access to these data; how we can improve discovery/access to data across DAAC’s (e.g, FI data archived in multiple DAACs)? DAAC’s continue to share knowledge and best practices to improve the data lifecycle.

Session 3: Working Groups

In the third session, representatives from several ESDS and ESDIS supported groups and working groups discussed their objectives, long-term vision, activities, and solicited input/collaboration with attendees. Table 2 presents a summary of these discussions.

Table 2: Summary of Groups and Working Groups discussions in Session 3

Group / Working Group Representative	Objectives	Long-term Vision	Activities

<p>Variable-First Services <i>Valerie Dixon</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Document definitions of a variable - Assess UMM-Variable needs for discovery & subsetting use cases <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Redlines to UMM-Var - 2024 ESDSWG Mtg 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Once HQ's Web Unification metadata priority work wraps up: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ask Metadata Stewardship Team to address residual discussion items - Create a Best Practices wiki for Variables per ESDSWG guidance - Update & release UMM-Variables schema accordingly - Revive ESDSWG to assess UMM-Variable needs for remaining Use Cases <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reformatting, Averaging, Regridding, Resampling, Aggregation - Improve GCMD Keywords to enable semantically consistent variables 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Metadata Stewardship Team <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - For DAAC representatives to team up to work through shared issues of interest, like sub-orbital schema creation - Making GCMD Keywords a truly semantic ontology <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Pending Project and HQ priorities & resources
<p>Airborne Data Management Group (ADMG) <i>Stephanie Wingo</i></p>	<p>Improving processes & guidelines for agency suborbital Earth observations Inventory of NASA Field Campaigns to support data discovery, findability, access (CASEI) Identify best practices for suborbital data stewardship</p>	<p>Increased scientific finding return on NASA's investment in suborbital Earth science observations from the past and future Fully leveraged field data supporting model and sensor validation studies, process elucidation, and variability & change assessment</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CASEI resource is now beyond beta-release and a key part of the NASA Airborne & Field Resource Center - Incremental CASEI feature improvements based on user input (eg: data products, tracks) - Process, recommendations, guidance, communication improvements to benefit multiple stakeholders - EVS-3 Projects: DMP & IIP requirements, timely data transfer, documentation updates - Ready to support EVS-4! - Data accession support for ESDS/HQ: summaries & recommendations for new and historical data
<p>Airborne & Field</p>	<p>Designed to help users find information about</p>	<p>Continue to enhance and add content to the</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Released the AFDRC - Published the 2022

<p>Data Resource Center (AFDRC) <i>Jennifer Brennan</i></p>	<p>NASA's airborne and field campaign suborbital measurements and instruments; provide tools and services to help users find, access, visualize and work with the data; and point users to learning resources for working with these unique data products.</p>	<p>AFDRC to be a single entry point for efficient data discovery, data access, user education, services hub, information and data documentation guidance.</p>	<p>Workshop Summary Report - Planned and executed the 2024 Workshop</p>
<p>Airborne & Field Data Working Group (AFDWG) <i>Michele Thornton</i></p>	<p>A working group that brings together ESDIS representatives, data centers, ADMG/CASEI, and other relevant entities to share, discuss, and generate solutions around the common objective of improving curation, publication, and use of airborne and field data.</p>	<p>To provide a collective and collaborative environment to share ideas and opportunities across and among the different types of airborne and field campaign measurements and instruments toward standardization and tools and services to improve discoverability, access, and visualization of suborbital data</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Review and publication of First Airborne and Field Workshop results - Collective ESCO review and implementation of consistent suborbital terminology as provided by the Catalog of Archived Suborbital Earth Science Investigations (CASEI) - Efforts toward variable standard naming conventions - Identification of discrete Campaign/Investigation files from Facility Instrument collections across DAACs - Collective contributions to the creation of the Airborne and Field Data Resource Center
<p>ESDIS O'FAIR Working Group <i>Ge Peng</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Support implementation of the SPD-41a; - Explore the current landscape of community FAIR practices; - Develop a practical guidance document for FAIR NASA SMD-funded Earth science data products. 	<p>Seamless data and information sharing, integration, and exchanges among NASA tools and systems, across agencies that manage Earth science data products, and across disciplines.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Going forward all NASA funded data products should follow FAIR. Existing missions and investigations are encouraged to do so. - Example O'FAIR recommendation: Assign and maintain a Digital Object Identifier (DOI), a globally unique and persistent identifier, to the satellite mission or field campaign and ensure that the DOI is

			resolved to a permanent mission/campaign landing page and explicitly embedded as structured, machine-actionable metadata, utilizing standards for linked data on the web.
<p>PCS for Airborne & Field Data <i>Matt Donovan</i></p>	<p>Thorough review and updates to implementation guide based on practitioner input, identified ambiguities, and illustrative examples Introduce Science Teams to PCS-kinds of requirements as early as possible Document and raise awareness of breakdown/pain points, gaps in understanding/clarity Seek new methods to streamline requirement compliance and long-term maintenance</p>	<p>Align the vision of the PCS with the resources available to mission teams and researchers, as well as to the DAACs. Share the burden of saving and collecting provenance from the earliest stage of mission planning to the last data product archived.</p>	<p>DAACs who archive airborne and field data are requested to review and comment on the PCS as well as its implementation guide (ORNL and NSIDC have done this). Open iterative ESCO review Address disconnect between Data Management Plan content creation and PCS expectations - Airborne and field provenance most efficiently collected during active campaign phase. - Mission teams and researchers are stakeholders; review their burden and costs related to PCS requirements.</p>
<p>ESDS Standards Coordination Office (ESCO) <i>Beth Huffer</i></p>	<p>-Provide access to standards, information, and templates to data producers and data providers. - Manage documentation and standards through a configuration control process involving reviews and comments from all affected organizations.</p>	<p>- Maintain a portal of templates and information about standard practices to improve data interoperability, data access, data discovery, and data use.</p>	<p>Recent ESCO-Approved standard: - Atmospheric Composition Variable Standard Names (Convention) - Data Product Development Guide for Data Producers (V2.0) -STAC format: json based format for describing geographical features of data - Cloud-optimized GeoTIFF</p>
<p>Applied Remote</p>	<p>ARSET's mission is to increase the use of EO in</p>	<p>To promote awareness and application of</p>	<p>Biodiversity Applications for</p>

<p>Sensing Training Program (ARSET) <i>Brock Blevins</i></p>	<p>decision making through training activities. -Cost-free training on the use of Earth Observations for decision making -Online and in-person -Live and instructor-led, or self-guided -Provided at no cost, with materials and recordings available from our website -Often multi-lingual -Range in level from introductory to advanced</p>	<p>NASA’s suborbital Earth observations To provide end-user feedback to sub-orbital campaigns (accessibility, data formats, etc.)</p>	<p>Airborne Imaging Systems: March 27, 2023 - April 05, 2023 [link was active through Jan 2025] This four-part training highlighted the use of hyperspectral Visible to Shortwave Infrared (VSWIR) imaging spectroscopy data for measuring and monitoring terrestrial and aquatic biodiversity (e.g., mapping plant or phytoplankton functional types). The series focused on using thermal and LiDAR data for characterizing the structure and function of ecosystems using airborne campaigns including the Hyperspectral Thermal Emission Spectrometer (HyTES) and NASA’s Land, Vegetation, and Ice Sensor (LVIS). 1,342 participants from 108 countries and 44 US states. 893 unique organizations were represented. Upcoming In-person training (BioSCape) Oct 7-11 2024</p>
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After concluding discussions in Session 3, a consensus request arose to add an [Earthdata Pub link](#) to the AFDRC page for all the DAACs, and the following main question:

“How do CMR, CASEI, SDE, and any other search tools relate with regards to airborne data?”

- The overall goal is towards one common metadata repository to feed all these tools (CASEI has its own metadata repository as CMR doesn’t have all the necessary fields).
- Earthdata Search is a logical starting place to search for airborne data, however it was not designed to convey specific situational and contextual details.
- The Science Discovery Engine (SDE) is designed to pull from multiple sources -- not just CMR -- particularly to support interdisciplinary science across all of NASA’s science divisions (not just Earth Science).

Workshop Overview Day 2:

Discussion topics for Day 2 focused on understanding perspectives of scientists across a range of disciplines and breakout sessions centered on participant-driven themes.

Session 4: Where are we going?

Day 2 opened with NASA HQ personnel providing a high level overview of the agency's vision for the future of ESDS as science needs, technological changes, governing policies, data requirements, and best practices continue to evolve.

Cerese Albers, Program Executive for ESDS at NASA Headquarters, set a forward-looking tone with an overview of current and planned data holdings, progress on ESDIS' transition to cloud infrastructure, including highlights from the Earthdata cloud initiative, and detailed the agency's newly updated Earth Science to Action Strategy (Fig 1) and how ESDS is evolving to meet needs for delivering actionable science. This evolution for ESDS includes the ongoing cloud migration, scaling of enterprise tools and streamlining through web unification, as well as crafting a vision for the future of NASA's Earth science data archives and user experiences. She also noted recent updates for flight missions and encouraged all in attendance to join the NASA Transform to Open Science (TOPS) initiative by earning the TOPS Open Science Certification.

Figure 1: The Earth Science to Action Strategy is meant to enhance the impact of NASA Earth Science to meet urgent human challenges. ESDS supports and enables every aspect, particularly as a vehicle to advance discovery via open science alongside well established service levels and mission operations [slide from Cerese Albers].

Following the HQ context, Rita Grullon-Pingon, Deputy Project Manager for Science Operations at ESDIS, presented an overview of the NASA ESDIS project and a multi-year strategy for streamlining the enterprise. Her remarks noted the importance of DAAC activities and interactions of DAACs with their respective scientific communities via User Working Groups and the Earthdata Forum. Details on the architecture involved for the Earthdata Cloud (EDC) transition were also mentioned (Fig 2), with an emphasis on plans for existing user workflows not changing significantly, but will eventually offer more research pathway opportunities for studies combining airborne and/or field data with larger satellite datasets.

Figure 2: Overview of the Earthdata Cloud (EDC) architecture for ESDIS [slide from Rita Grullon-Pingon].

Ensuing discussion and comments provided the following key points:

- Interoperability and inconsistencies are seen as current, important challenges for airborne and field data
- Can AI/ML tools be developed to support initial processing of data and automate data/metadata standards adherence? Can this support scaling and later analysis?
- Data discovery needs to support searching for a specific metric (variable) over a user-defined area and/or time of interest

Session 5: Stewards & Scientists Panel

Following the DAAC-centric updates on Day 1, Session 5 on Day 2 focused on connecting the roles and activities of NASA’s data stewardship professionals to current and emerging community needs from airborne and field science practitioners. The session format included a brief introduction from each scientist on their work involving suborbital observations followed by a moderated open discussion.

An overview of key comments from each panelist is included in Table 3:

Table 3: Summary of panelists and discussion comments from Session 5

Name Primary Affiliation	Topical Area(s)	Key Comments
Daryl Yang <i>ORNL DAAC</i>	Arctic/boreal region ecology, Imaging spectroscopy, Thermal remote sensing, Data-model integrations (ABoVE and NGEE campaigns)	Better characterize and understand the vegetation distribution and the function of trees Developing a Collection focusing on remote sensing, scaling for advancing Arctic ecology
Dana Chadwick <i>NASA / JPL</i>	EMIT Mission Applications	How to scale imaging? Spectroscopy data for vegetation kind of science and applications Integration of terrestrial data collections with airborne data
Owen Cooper <i>NOAA Chemical Sciences Lab</i>	Tropospheric ozone	Ozones on monitoring stations, only launch once per week, only get 4 profiles in a month Western North America to come up with a reliable 25 year trend, aircraft data really filled in the gap Big fan of aircraft data
HP Marshall <i>Boise State University</i>	Lidar/radar/SAR remote sensing of snow over various surface and topographic areas (SnowEx, CryoGARS campaigns)	Snow-X, Efforts that don't involve a lot of aircraft data The value of using the facility instrument was really apparent. We got really high quality data
Kristen Rasmussen <i>Colorado State University</i>	Precipitation science and convective processes (INCUS campaign)	Focus on investigation of convective updraft, our goal is to understand why when and where tropical convective forms Plan smaller scale experiments in Colorado, Alabama, and Oklahoma to collect field observations during the spring and summer to test some of our Incas science objectives.

<p>Gerald Heymsfield <i>NASA GSFC</i></p>	<p>Precipitation science and remote sensing, airborne in situ and remote sensing (IMPACTS campaign)</p>	<p>IMPACTS - 3 years of aircraft flights. Mission to study Snow storms on the East Coast</p>
<p>Fredrick Bingham <i>University of North Carolina - Wilmington</i></p>	<p>Data management and applications, ocean salinity and stratification, ocean dynamics (S-MODE campaign)</p>	<p>Ocean surface solidity its connection to the global water cycle Looking a lot at the seasonal aspects of of variability in the surface solidity Connection to the global water cycle.</p>

The open discussion portion of Session 5, moderated by Stephanie Wingo, gravitated to several key areas:

Panelists expressed a consensus that the availability of tutorials designed for specific use cases are very helpful. Also, they expressed a need for Jupyter notebooks that have everything one would need to access and initially plot data that would be useful for early data interrogation tasks and promote data reuse. Kristen Rasmussen of Colorado State University and team scientist with the Investigation of Convective Updrafts (INCUS) Mission is already working on visualization tools like Jupyter notebooks and tutorials to train scientists looking at the forthcoming campaign's observations.

The panel was asked to comment on optional storage/location for these types of learning resources. Responses were:

- Store them in the GitHub repository that is linked to the data page
- Jupyter notebooks attached to a binder
- Like the idea of having them with the dataset itself, ie: on the dataset landing page
- Integrate with the field datasets that are being archived, basically click on it and it visualizes the data.

Discussion also touched on the myriad challenges of working with airborne and field data. Owen Cooper of the NOAA Chemical Science Lab mentioned that even discoverability is a challenge, as there are so many aircraft campaigns not just from NASA but other groups around the world. It would be helpful to have tools for data discoverability, ideally across many agencies/entities, that would allow a user to scan across all the different airborne campaigns at once to find the needed data. Other challenges voiced by the panelists included:

- Struggles with data versioning
- Standardization of file names
- Data files should have all the variables described

Dana Chadwick, JPL scientist with EMIT, talked about the PI review stage, and how to get co-authors to review and comment, especially when the review is on a static web page. This makes it very hard to edit or track changes. Frederick Bingham, an S-MODE (a NASA EVS-3 campaign) team member from UNC Wilmington, mentioned several issues with data publication and a lack of an easy way to upload very large data sets to AWS. He mentioned a need for the ability to distribute datasets within a science team before the data are formally published and for a consistent way to keep updated on the data publication process.

The panelists stated they generally have had good experiences working with multiple DAACs, *especially when the DAAC assignment for a field investigation occurs prior to field data collection*. This provides ample opportunity to establish a clear data pipeline and a mutual understanding of data product, metadata, and documentation requirements before data is collected.

This was followed by a discussion of CASEI, which covered multiple needs ranging from having the ability to perform faceted searches to find data to how the information is populated and curated on CASEI. NASA has a long history of airborne and field campaigns and identifying and curating metadata for legacy missions takes time.

The panelists discussed unmet data aggregation and interrogation needs, from a scientific standpoint:

- *The ability to merge multiple data sets and variables into one file for download.*
This would reduce the level of effort from having to download lots of different files in different formats, even from the same flight.
- *Integrate field and airborne data for algorithm development.*
Using notebooks to do some of those merges in a specific way and then people can build off of them, but help is needed with satellite instruments, development, validation, calibration and other aspects.

Panelists also discussed evaluating satellite data with aircraft and field data. Aircraft data can be spotty and limited and trying to line up satellite granules with the aircraft data in exact locations is a challenge. Thus, *a utility to match up aircraft flight tracks and satellite data and/or instrument swaths* would be very helpful.

The final topic was the unique data challenges for inter-agency airborne and field campaigns. These include:

- Different accounts (and authentication steps) and data structures at different agencies
- Getting data from campaigns that cover multiple countries and cross borders.
- Data policy requirements differ among agencies

Session 6: Investment Vote Activity, Breakout Sessions

In the final session block of the workshop, participants were asked to prioritize the areas they view as most important for addressing needs for airborne and field Earth science data at NASA. This was framed as an “investment voting” activity. This activity was moderated by Yaxing Wei, the ORNL DAAC’s lead scientist, and facilitated via the OpinionX stack ranking platform.

Participants were each given a simplified budget of \$10 to “invest” in their choice of areas listed below. With no requirement to put all of their “budget” on any one topic, participants were asked to allocate votes (1 vote = \$1 of their budget) to the areas they thought would be most impactful.

Results (Table 4) indicate the highest priority of the workshop participants is for additional/expanded tutorials and training, advancing consistency and metadata standards across DAACs, and visualizations for airborne and field data. These three highly-valued topics were then assigned as the focus for breakout discussions in the last major session of the workshop.

Table 4: Results from the Investment Voting Activity in Session 6. Topics in the blue shading were used for breakout sessions in the latter portion of the Session.

Rank	Topic	Total Votes	Percent Preferred
1	Tutorials and Trainings*	45	20.5 %
2	Metadata standards & advancing convention consistency (files, variables) across DAACs	40	18.2 %
3	Needs & challenges for quick visualization of airborne & field observations	38	17.3 %
4	Combining airborne and/or field data with satellite observations	31	14.1 %
5	Airborne & field data in the cloud	24	10.9 %
6	Data Rescue: missing/historical data*	22	10. %
7	Data publication & transfer*	20	9. %

**These options were added based on participants’ input throughout the event.*

Breakout Sessions

The final workshop sessions offered a space for participants to compile ideas and document known difficulties in the top three areas from the voting activity. Attendees were given a choice of which breakout session(s) to attend, and they were asked to document their attendance and participation in separate notes documents for each breakout session. Participants reconvened to a single session to summarize the breakout discussions, as shown in Table 5.

Table 5: Summary of breakout session discussions based on participant-driven topic selections

Breakout Session	Discussion Summary
Tutorials & Trainings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● More are better - however, time and resources are our biggest challenges. Good method to find out what types of trainings the community wants the most <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Templates could be quick/easy-win - if there's enterprise resources that could help and be used by the DAACs ○ Potential for cross-DAAC trainings; however with differences in data there will be DAAC specific trainings ○ Series of airborne deep-dives (probably individual DAACs): "AFDWG Presents"
Consistency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● For consistency, the reason is to have more and more automation (both internally and for users). Easier to use, transform data. We want to be able to slice and dice data. To facilitate this, we need robust and consistent metadata. Machine actionability is the essence of FAIR. Start with the end in mind. Use data with as little human intervention as possible. Brings about the point of semantic consistency. ● Concern that increasing consistency can go hand in hand with decreasing scrutiny on the part of the end user. The more we automate things, the greater the risk of misuse. That already happens, so there is an increased risk to go with the benefits of automation. How to make it more obvious to users where to go to find more information and read the documentation. And who actually reads documentation? ● The quality of the metadata is important. It's a difficult issue that can be a black hole for time, continually working on the quality of the metadata. What's important for metadata curators and scientists is to work together on metadata and provide expertise in their own ways. Better collaboration is important. MD curators often don't have a science background. ● Datasets should be peer reviewed, no substitute for a human taking a look at data. ● Having controlled vocabularies where definitions can be agreed on can help with the quality issue, good descriptions are important. ● Establishing conventions and adding things to controlled vocabularies can be a time consuming process. ● Are we interested in considering the value of tools for creating metadata, or do we need better tools? There are already some tools, sometimes even more than one per DAAC. Is it worth considering how we might consolidate and get better consistency in metadata by consolidating/getting better tools. Ties back to the point about training and tutorials for data producers – which also ties back into the early DAAC engagement in a process to help shape the data pipelines in ways that are more robust and reliable.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The value of early engagement was demonstrated with Delta-X, which helped in getting better consistency and adherence to standards up front.
Visualization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The ability to pick a campaign, pick a variable, and show all the flight tracks with some indication of altitude. • Geographical selections - pick a place/box, altitude range, and tell me all the data for [variable x] • Trajectory data requires consistent input data: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Many aircraft/nav data have inconsistencies ○ Don't use "trajectory" to mean flight track (terminology) • Facility Instruments: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Think of campaigns more holistically to build out better polygon-type files for representing flight paths. ○ Include consideration of flight path vs. instrument swath • Altitude is really important!!! Shading to indicate? Units consistency • What about different kinds of observations of the variable? In situ vs remote? Ozone eg: in situ? Lidar?

Workshop Findings and Participant Input

Over the two-day workshop, more than 75 attendees shared their experiences using, producing, and stewarding NASA airborne and field data. Participants of varied backgrounds and experience levels (Appendix B) suggested improvements through community members' presentations, breakout discussions, chat comments, panel discussions, and Slido polls (see examples in Appendix C). The variety of communication methods used during this fully virtual event ensured all attendees had an opportunity to participate and voice their ideas.

Workshop feedback came from the registration form questions, comments captured during discussions, and a thorough review of session notes, recordings, and transcripts. The workshop team reviewed, discussed, and tabulated the feedback for each session to synthesize the workshop feedback into common themes and actionable items. Samples of individual feedback items from several of the workshop sessions are provided in Appendix C below.

For students with no prior experience working with airborne and field data, a common theme was findability and use. For example, *“The most challenging aspect of accessing NASA airborne and field data is navigating the vast array of datasets, ensuring compatibility, and interpreting metadata accurately. Additionally, inconsistencies in metadata and ongoing user feedback are hurdles in maximizing the usability of the data.”*

Among all registrants the *“consistency of metadata”* and *“the quality and consistency of metadata”* were commonly noted challenges in discovering and using data. Many workshop participants commented on challenges with findability/discovery and access:

- *“There are a lot of different avenues to access NASA data”*

- “The amount of data is spread out”
- “Need to find a systematic archive storing all the NASA airborne data”
- “Findability for a desired region”

Attendees also commented on the need for *improving filtering* of search results when a large number of collections are returned, as well as a desire for finding and/or searching a full list of the *variables (or parameters, or measurements)* campaigns measure. Being able to find/discover airborne and field data *across agencies* was another concern for participants.

2024 Workshop Feedback Categories

Once every item of feedback was tabulated from all sessions, the workshop team sorted each item to conceptual categories, starting with the same set of categories used for feedback from the 2022 Workshop as outlined in the [previous workshop report](#).

The 2024 Workshop focused on obtaining feedback from participants about challenges with discovery, findability, access, and use of NASA Airborne and Field Data, which resulted in fewer categories. During the process of sorting the feedback into categories to identify common themes, it became apparent there were relational overlaps among categories. For example, to improve metadata consistency and data formats for interoperability, ESCO standards for airborne and field data would require an update that would be communicated to DAACs and data producers to ensure compliance.

After considering these types of overlaps and the common threads among individual feedback items, the workshop team distilled the 2024 Workshop participants’ feedback into the following six categories. From within each of the identified categories, the workshop team further elucidated several common themes in participants’ feedback (see details in Appendix D), which were used to further group the feedback items to assess what key actions are needed.

2024 Feedback Categories

Key Actions Needed Based on Feedback

After the feedback items were categorized and themes identified, the AFDWG further distilled the information by identifying and summarizing the key actions indicated or requested by the workshop participants. From this effort, the remaining generalized findings within each feedback category were identified:

Tools and Services

- Visualization:
 - Develop tools and/or notebooks for visualizing and harmonizing data from multiple campaigns.
 - Develop the ability to visualize flight path vs. instrument swath.
 - Provide the ability to pick a campaign and a variable to display all flight tracks.
 - Consolidate visualization tools as they encompass many websites.
 - Users would like GIS visualization of facility instruments.
- Discoverability:
 - Users would like a tool for discoverability to scan across multiple campaigns, deployments, etc.
 - Users need a way to find corresponding satellite granules/observations based on airborne and field data information (coincident data).
 - Provide the ability to integrate field data in specific satellite tools/services (Ex: SOTO, HITIDE).
- Subsetting Challenges:
 - Spatiotemporal subsetting and subsetting across multiple inconsistent formats is a challenge.

Key Actions Indicated or Requested:

- *Conduct assessment of current visualization tools and services, notebooks, etc. Conduct gap analysis based on workshop feedback, and create a plan. Will Web Unification address “visualization tools encompass many websites”?*
- *Identify and prioritize enhancements to Earthdata Search, CMR, Harmony, etc. to encompass user requests for discovering and using suborbital data.*

Communications/Outreach:

- Awareness and Notification:
 - Users desire a notification method for new versions of a data product they have previously used.
 - Provide notifications of status during the data publication process, updates to available training resources, and general platform updates (acquisition/retirement of platforms, eg: DC-8, 777).

- Improve communications/notifications provided to DAACs, ScienceTeams, and Data Users about data products, publication process, and visualization updates/changes.
- Simplify Access to Existing Training/Resources – Proposed Airborne & Field Data Resource Center Updates:
 - Include organized links to existing tutorials, Openscapes, and other training materials in the current AFDRC page.
 - These exist but are not easily accessible from within AFDRC. Streamline entry points for help desk, Earthdata Forum, Openscape tutorials, Earthdata Pub, ARSET, and webinars.
- Topics for New Training/Information Resources:
 - Develop tutorials with specific use cases that can target key audiences based on experience level. Examples: high school users learn to access and use data; Openscapes data recipes and Jupyter notebooks; AWS interface, working with data in the cloud; multi-DAAC “AFDWG Presents” type webinars/workshops; synergistic airborne/spaceborne data examples/tutorials – *to enable actionable science!*
 - “More ‘how-to’ sessions for various communities, based on science domains”.
 - “Tutorial development with use cases have been very valuable”. This is a specific comment that supported continuing these types of efforts.
- Communication on Workshop Itself:
 - Share progress on goals/achievements as they happen.
 - Communicate highlighted user needs (key for both DAACs/ESDIS/ADMG as well as users to know their priorities are heard).
 - AFDWG may benefit from closer ties with the ARSET team for training development; field data is part of many trainings, but not as prominent in discussions.
 - “More coordination with working groups and activities happening throughout the community”.

Key Actions Indicated or Requested:

- *Investigate using NASA social media and Earthdata (Resource Spotlight, News & Events, & Blog) to provide the user community and stakeholders notifications about data, training resources, product status, Workshop progress, etc.*
 - *Include possible notifications of new version releases for data products a user has previously accessed or downloaded.*
- *Streamline and improve access to training and resource material on the AFDRC.*
- *Review existing training material, identify gaps based on workshop feedback, develop a plan, and coordinate cross-DAAC effort to address gaps. Work with ARSET.*

Open Science:

- Continue support for Open Science:
 - Focus on discovery, usability and SPD-41a future policies, figure out how suborbital fits in, and how to bring data to the most potential users :
- Jupyter Notebooks:
 - Users would like Jupyter notebooks linked to the data and/or linked with Binder, run notebooks with single click and to have the ability to reproduce figures in a journal paper that describes the data.
 - Develop notebooks that have everything needed to access and plot data.
 - It would be useful to have notebooks in a repo (Ex. GitHub) linked to a data/campaign landing page with examples to help users.
 - DAAC notebooks that integrate with other datasets archived at the DAAC to visualize data would be useful.
- Data in the cloud and cloud ready data:
 - Provide users with analysis ready datasets and a platform in the cloud to leverage multiple datasets in the cloud for data analysis, assimilations, visualization, etc.

Key Actions Indicated or Requested:

- *ADMG & DAACs spearhead the effort for greater involvement in Open Science from the suborbital community.*
- *Analysis of data transformation services level of effort to transform suborbital data into cloud-ready data.*
- *Facilitate cloud-based analysis (platform as a Service) to support users who would prefer to do data analysis in the cloud; one option is well structured/documented Jupyter Notebooks.*
- *Develop a Jupyter Notebook best practices document, similar to a Data Management Plan (DMP), or the Preservation Content Specifications (PCS), to address workshop feedback and reinforce Open Science.*

Search & Discovery:

- Accessibility and Findability (already exists):
 - Improve satellite user community's ease of access to Airborne and Field Data to support calibration/validation efforts for satellite missions.
 - Improve overall accessibility to the data, to the documentation of the data and field campaign/mission information, etc.
 - Current data tutorials, flight catalog with orbital overpass.
- Searching for Data:
 - Improve the ability to search across datasets and within larger data volumes.
 - Improve ability to find relevant search results through filtering and variable-based searching, etc.
 - Explore opportunities to improve searching data from CASEI.

- Discoverability (didn't know existed before):
 - Expand tools for data discovery to scan across all airborne campaigns at once.
 - Improve the discovery of NASA Airborne and Field data across DAACs.
 - Develop search abilities for a specific variable for a defined area of interest or a specific variable and/or data within campaigns (How would a user know which campaigns have specific data?).
 - Use resources precisely in gathering information.
- Identifying and Locating data and information:
 - Workshop participants provided feedback on the following challenges; identifying geochemical composition of observation, dataset descriptions, info on measurement uncertainties, geophysical and geological aspects of observations, and discovery of data over a specific region (temporal/spatial search, variable-based searching).
 - Feedback on CASEI: Users want to be able to discover specific information: specify a region, an altitude range, and the time range and get all of a specific variable (e.g. ozone); continue to add older airborne campaigns.

Key Actions Indicated or Requested:

- *Identify enhancements, updates to Earthdata Search, CMR, and product metadata for improving accessibility and findability. (Note: Web Unification will, theoretically, enable a streamlined approach to search and discovery of documentation, tutorials, etc.)*
 - *The UMM may need updating as well as product metadata once the identified underlying components of Earthdata Search that handle filtering, variable-based searching, and temporal-spatial searching, etc. are reviewed for metadata deficiencies as well as making recommendations to address user feedback.*
 - *Web Unification should improve discovery of AFD across DAACs.*
 - *Ensure DAACs are collecting and disseminating information about resources used in/during a Field Campaign.*
 - *Holistic review of CASEI (objectives) and future app expectations*

Standards & Metadata (Data Management Requirements):

- Interoperability:
 - Improve data interoperability, ex. ENVI to netCDF.
 - Explore Cloud optimized formats (Zarr, COG, etc.).
 - Develop a cloud-based metadata compliance checker.
- Metadata Standards:
 - Develop metadata templates for common field data types (trajectories, swath, profiles), file formats, etc.
 - Suborbital field data processing levels need updating to ensure they are applicable to field observations.

- Continue to improve semantics and vocabulary. Use GCMD keywords and controlled vocabularies where definitions can be agreed on; use filename conventions for airborne and field data
- ASCII and netCDF/HDF files should have all the variables described and standard formats.
- Incorporate metadata standards into data product structure before transfer to the DAAC.
- Improve distribution by standardizing datasets within the campaign science team, ideally prior to data transfer to the DAAC(s), at minimum before data publication by the DAAC.
- There is a need for verification and validation of data in CASEI.
- Improve Consistency:
 - Ensure consistency early with engagements with science teams.
 - Improve consistency among DAACs.
 - Provide guidance for robust and consistent metadata.
 - Provide a more consistent user experience by improving semantics, file and variable name conventions, variable level delineations, and data formats.
 - Improves the consistency of metadata and documentation of variables in a dataset.
 - Variable names should be labeled the same way across campaigns and DAACs (Climate and Forecast (CF) standards).
 - Keep data producers updated on the data publication process.
 - Note: *Quality of the metadata is important. This is a difficult issue. Metadata can be a black hole for time, with data producers continually working on the quality of the metadata. It is important for metadata curators and scientists to work together on metadata and provide expertise in their own ways. Better collaboration is important. Metadata curators often don't have a science background.*

Key Actions Indicated or Requested:

- *Interoperability: DAACs work closely with Science Teams on V&V (verification and validation) of data products and work closely with Science Teams to investigate generating **cloud-optimized data** products.*
- *Metadata Standards: Identify and document gaps in Airborne and Field Data metadata. Work with Airborne/Field DAACs and CMR/GCMD to recommend and implement solutions to address metadata gaps and opportunities to advance access and use across the enterprise.*
- *Improve Consistency: Work with ESDIS on early DAAC assignment to ensure DAACs can initiate early engagement with Science Teams providing guidance, V&V on naming conventions, data formats, documentations, PCS materials, etc. DAACs should have a kickoff session with the Science Team to explain the benefits of using standards resulting in consistency across Airborne and Field Data products.*

- *Note: <https://analytics.cal-adapt.org/data/standards/>*
- *Continue UxS Community of Practice for data format & metadata conventions across agencies (NOAA, NASA, USGS)*

Programmatic:

- **Interagency Airborne and Field Campaigns:**
 - Users would like the ability to discover, find, access data, observations across agencies (NASA, NOAA, ESA, USGS, etc.).
 - There are too many access and discovery routes. This creates confusion and is challenging - even for data within the same agency!
- **Cloud-based platform:**
 - Users would like the ability to do data processing and interaction across NASA DAACs, including analysis in place.
 - Develop new AI/ML tools to help non-RS (research scientist) users to process/interrogate, use, visualize, and initially interpret the data.
 - Request for new cross-agency capability to store and use new data types like UxS (uncrewed observation systems, aerial water etc).
 - Users would like compatibility and interoperability between AWS and GDG (google developer group cloud).
- **Data Publication Lifecycle:**
 - The time required for data transfer to a DAAC, archival and publication process is challenging; archiving large data volumes is challenging.
 - Coordinate data products with user guides when data is released to the community.
 - Users would like access to ancillary/contextual information and documentation, such as flight reports, etc. Getting access is challenging.
 - Enforce data standards across the DAACs for consistent user experience.
 - Improve processes between DAACs to lessen inconsistencies.
 - Identify methods for reviewing and incorporating “community standards” in ESDIS standards where applicable.
 - Assign a DAAC early in the process to work closely with science teams.
 - Address any disconnect between DMP content creation and PCS expectations; ensure PCS information is captured and archived with appropriate data products.
 - Document Facility instruments processes, including data processing, publication pipeline, etc.
 - Users identified data downloading as challenging due to large file sizes, inconsistencies with data filenames, and spanning multiple agencies.

Key Actions Indicated or Requested:

- *Work with ESDIS to investigate interagency data sharing agreements to consolidate data access and discovery entry points.*
- *Develop a business use case by investigating the strategies used by MAAP and cal-adapt.org (cloud-based platform) to recommend to ESDIS an airborne and field data analysis center.*
- *Data Publication Lifecycle: Consider developing a PCS-like check-list for DAACs to follow - a new feature for Earthdata Pub to provide transparency, akin to a “public” Earthdata pub dashboard showing data publication progress*

2022 and 2024 Workshops as a Whole

The feedback from the 2022 Workshop provided a prioritized list of 12 recommendations for the Airborne and Field Data Working Group (AFDWG). [The full 2022 report can be found here.](#) The 2024 Workshop feedback was generally aligned with recommendations from the 2022 Workshop, with a focus on continuing improvements for data discovery, findability, access and use. For example, the top recommendation from the 2022 Workshop was “[Assign DAACs to campaigns as soon as possible after the award.](#)”

Early DAAC assignment is essential for all NASA projects that collect or generate data - and critical for the success of airborne and field projects. While there is variability in each field investigation’s timeline, overall, DAAC assignment is now occurring earlier, and with a more streamlined process, as evident in the EVS-3 series of campaigns.

Feedback from the 2024 Workshop included “improve data consistency”, which is easier if DAACs can work with data producers early in the data life cycle. It was recommended that AFDWG work with ESDIS on early DAAC assignment to ensure DAACs can initiate engagement with the science teams to provide guidance on file naming conventions, data formats, documentations, and to verify and validate that data are in compliance with ESDIS standards. When appropriate, DAACs should hold a kickoff session with the science team to explain the benefits of using standards to support consistency across airborne and field data products. This also addresses recommendations from the 2022 Workshop to “[Improve usability and interoperability of disparate data formats,](#)” and “[Improve usability and interoperability of disparate data formats.](#)” 2024 Workshop participants also recommended that DAACs work closely with science teams to explore generating cloud-optimized data products and to facilitate adherence to open science principles. For example, in July 2024, NASA released [Version 2.0 of the Data Product Development Guide \(DPDG\) for Data Producers.](#) The DPDG provides key information for developing Earth Science data products derived from remote sensing and in situ data, and now includes updated information on topics such as formatting data for use in cloud

environments and leveraging metadata to increase the findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability ([FAIR](#) principles) of NASA datasets.

The AFDRC was launched in late 2023, in response to the 2022 Workshop recommendation to “[Develop an Airborne and Field Data Resource Center \(AFDRC\) on Earthdata](#)”. Participants who attended the 2022 workshop, and subsequently reviewed the AFDRC after it went live, suggested additional streamlining of the page and more training resources be added. Based on the 2022 and 2024 feedback, the AFDWG aims to identify gaps and develop a cross-DAAC plan to address lingering needs, leveraging ARSET training material where applicable, and look to coordinate the development of new training material with ARSET, if and when appropriate.

The 2022 and 2024 Workshop participants voiced concerns with having too many entry points for finding airborne and field data across multiple agencies (NASA, NOAA, USGS, etc.). Both groups recommend for AFDWG to work with ESDIS to investigate interagency data-sharing agreements to consolidate data access and discovery entry points.

The 2022 Workshop recommendations included “[Make modifications to CMR](#): Users have difficulty finding NASA airborne and field data in Earthdata search.” During the 2024 Workshop the committee heard similar challenges from participants with finding Airborne and Field Data. To improve the Search and Discovery of Airborne and Field Data, ESDIS, DAACs, and ADMG have already initiated efforts to address remaining deficiencies with CMR metadata in the context of airborne and field observations. The release of [the new Earthdata website](#), a multi-phase ESDS project to bring a consistent UI/UX experience across the enterprise, will enable a streamlined approach to search and discovery of documentation, tutorials, etc (this implies a gradual migration of content and entry points to the new web presence).

Participants at the 2024 workshop requested AFDWG pursue greater suborbital community involvement in NASA’s Open Science initiative. Discussions focused on how non-satellite observations relate to agency efforts to advance data discovery, usability, and policies such as SPD-41a.

Working Group 2024 Recommendations

Based on participants’ input at the 2024 workshop and the evolution of activities initiated after the 2022 event, the AFDWG presents the following recommendations:

- ***Simplify access points and streamline tools and services:*** A common piece of input from participants, on nearly any topic, was that there exist too many pathways for current users to access data, tools and services, which can create confusion. Several of the recommendations below tie directly into the need for a simplified user experience.

Feedback Categories:

Search & Discovery, Communication & Outreach, Tools & Services

- ***Improve metadata conventions, standards, and implementation to bolster discovery, interoperability, and utilization of cloud-based environments:*** Indicated actions across several themes focused on improvements to metadata for both consistency across current holdings as well as in support of future efforts.
 - ***Search & Discovery:*** Current search utilities are largely based on the CMR, which supports satellite-based observations very well. However, metadata that is more specific and contextually relevant than what presently exists in CMR is required to support advanced search and discovery capabilities for non-satellite data. Solutions are needed to address gaps in the current CMR, for the case of airborne and field observations, which may require augmentation of UMM metadata models. For example, to make airborne and field data more searchable by observation type, campaign, platform, instrument, geographic region, and multiple variables via Earthdata Search, new metadata fields for airborne-type data would need the UMM to be augmented. Existing portals such as Earthdata Search and Harmony should be optimized to support suborbital observations.
 - ***Metadata to support variable-based search and discovery:*** Users reiterated findings from the 2022 workshop and separate ADMG surveys indicating a strong desire for data product search capacity based on variable/observable, overlapping/coincident observations, and measurement method.
 - ***Consistency:*** Conventions, if not formal standards, must be developed and documented for metadata and data stewardship of airborne and field observations. This includes: data formats, naming conventions, supporting documentation, and PCS materials. Beginning field investigations with early science team involvement with respective data stewards can increase the prevalence of use of such conventions, further aiding in more efficient data stewardship.
 - ***Interoperability:*** Early DAAC involvement with science teams can integrate and advance best practices and standards for data formats, metadata, etc.
 - ***Cloud-optimization:*** Cloud optimization is the future. Stakeholders need to plan and work towards the new paradigm of being able to find, subset, visualize, interrogate, and use cloud-optimized and analysis-ready data products.

Feedback Categories:

Standards & Metadata, Search & Discovery, Tools & Services, Open Science

- ***Advance capabilities and simplify access to data and data visualization resources:***
 - ***Coincident satellite overpasses:*** Workshop participants requested the ability to search for/discover coincident satellite overpasses (both nadir tracks & specific instrument swaths) for airborne and field campaigns. Changes to CMR to store flight tracks and changes to Earthdata Search to display flight tracks would need to be explored and compared to alternative solutions.

- Resources like the FCX and ADV are currently only available at respective DAACs (GHRC and ORNL), but their capabilities would benefit users across all of ESDIS.
- **Tool Convergence:** An enterprise initiative is underway on this topic. The approach is to evaluate the services and tools across ESDIS with a focus on renewing the user experience to be as consistent as possible with a focus on increased value of individual resources. AFDWG will work closely with ESDIS, DAACs and ADMG to assess the current visualization tools and services, Jupyter notebooks, identify gaps, and make recommendations.
- **Simplify Access:** Workshop participants stated they are overwhelmed by the variety of tools and entry points offered through the DAACs and ESDIS. The aforementioned tool convergence initiative is also addressing this.

Feedback Categories:

Tools & Services, Search & Discovery, Communications & Outreach

- **Expand Communications Pathways:** Provide notifications of data product and version releases, training, tutorials, and user feedback solicitations. Workshop participants across all stages of their careers voiced a need for additional tutorials, Jupyter notebooks, and webinars. They also found it challenging to find these resources and events.
 - **Notification Pathways:** NASA, ESDIS, and the DAACs use several social media and other platforms to broadcast news, events, webinars, training, and other activities (Facebook, Instagram, LinkedIn, Youtube, etc.). AFDWG can work with DAACs and science teams to provide targeted awareness to communities of interest.
 - **Training Gaps:** Identify gaps in training content based on user input, develop plans to address cross-DAAC efforts and integrate with ARSET training where applicable. Workshop participants stressed a need for providing notifications of existing and future trainings, tutorials for:
 - New data users (students, early career) on how to access and use the data
 - Experienced data users (mid to late career) on using the cloud for data analysis

Feedback Categories:

Communications & Outreach, Tools & Services, Open Science

- **Support Open Science activities:** Workshop participants agreed DAACs should continue supporting Open Science activities. In 2023, NASA launched the [TOPS](#) initiative designed to rapidly transform agencies, organizations, and communities to an open paradigm that shares data and analysis methods (including code) to more rapidly advance scientific discoveries and further human understanding.
 - **Cloud Ready Data:** Several data transformation services exist within Earthdata. To address the need for specific cloud-ready data, ESDIS would need to analyze

current data transformation services to assess level of effort for generating cloud-ready data from existing archives.

- **Platform as a Service:** Workshop participants would like to bring their code, algorithms, and Jupyter notebooks to the data to alleviate the need of downloading data which would save time and costs. To support this activity, NASA would need to undertake a feasibility study and evaluate interest in “platform as a service” options to support analysis-in-the-cloud.
- **Open Science Resources:** Continue to support and more widely share (see communications recommendations) open science resources including well-structured/documented Jupyter Notebooks.
- **AFD Jupyter Notebooks:** Throughout the workshop, participants noted the value of Jupyter notebooks in supporting their research and for learning how to use airborne and field data (eg: BioScape Workshop). To support users and science teams it would be useful to have a *Developer's Guide to Best Practices for Open Source AFD Jupyter Notebooks*, similar to existing guidance for Data Management Plans (DMPs) and the Preservation Content Specification (PCS).

Feedback Categories:

Open Science, Programmatic & Process Aspects

- **Evaluate and improve programmatic and process aspects:** A holistic review of the ESDS and ESDIS governance policies will provide a baseline for building future improvements to addressing programmatic and process aspects gaps, decision-making, risk-management, and compliance.
 - **Reduce Entry Points:** The ESDS web unification project is one example effort aimed at reducing the number of entry points by bringing DAAC websites and SIPS into a central portal. ESDIS has also implemented a tools convergence project to review all tools across the enterprise, determine any overlaps, and suggest specific guidance on tools to keep, deprecate, and/or combine to provide the most value to the user community without losing functionality.
 - **Open Science & Cloud Adoption:** As NASA and other agencies continue to collect large volumes of data, workshop participants recommended pursuing cloud-optimized data formats, providing access to cloud resources, data sharing among agencies, and the development and sharing of Jupyter notebooks to reduce the burden of downloading data, working locally with large data volumes, navigating various data formats, and more.
 - Example: The [Multi-Mission Algorithm and Analysis Platform \(MAAP\)](#) is a joint effort between NASA and ESA (European Space Agency) designed to support collaborative research by bringing together relevant data, algorithms, and computing capabilities into a common cloud environment to address the challenges of sharing and processing data from field,

airborne, and satellite measurements related to NASA, ESA, and other space agency missions.

Feedback Categories:

Programmatics & Process Aspects, Standards & Metadata, Open Science

Conclusion

Over 80 participants attended the April 2024 Airborne and Field Data Workshop, which featured updates from ESDIS, ADMG, and the DAACs on improvements that had been made as a result of the 2022 workshop recommendations and provided data users with multiple opportunities to provide feedback on their ability to easily find, access, and use NASA suborbital data. After the workshop, the organizing committee met on a routine basis to categorize and analyze all feedback items. While sorting through the feedback, commonalities were found and six categories were identified: Communication and Outreach, Tools and Services, Standards and Metadata, Open Science, Search and Discovery, and Programmatic Aspects. Based on a holistic assessment of all gathered input, the following recommendations are proposed by the AFDWG:

- Simplify access points and streamline tools and services
Feedback Categories: Search & Discovery, Communication & Outreach, Tools & Services
- Improve metadata conventions, standards, and implementation to bolster discovery, interoperability, and utilization of cloud-based environments
Feedback Categories: Standards & Metadata, Search & Discovery, Tools & Services, Open Science
- Advance capabilities and simplify access to data and data visualization resources
Feedback Categories: Tools & Services, Search & Discovery, Communications & Outreach
- Expand Communications Pathways
Feedback Categories: Communications & Outreach, Tools & Services, Open Science
- Support Open Science activities
Feedback Categories: Open Science, Programmatic & Process Aspects
- Evaluate and improve programmatic and process aspects
Feedback Categories: Programmatics & Process Aspects, Standards & Metadata, Open Science

The top recommendations from the 2022 workshop, assigning DAACs earlier to campaigns and building out the AFDRRC, will also continue to be implemented as they are low cost and of high benefit to the suborbital community. Overall, this second workshop provided value to the committee and attendees as feedback and discussions presented a unique opportunity to share perspectives among and across groups of data users, data producers, and data stewards.

Lessons learned by the committee to apply to future workshops include:

- Since the workshop is held every two years, including HQ, ESDS, ESDIS, and select Working Group updates as these updates offer participants insight to agency and organization needs and priorities.
- Ensure future sessions are interactive and engaging to solicit as much participation and input as possible.
- Add a training or “how-to” session to allow more direct interaction with specific workshop participants and to get a first-hand look at struggles and pitfalls users experience with suborbital data (i.e., “A day in the life of a user”).

The AFDWG, per its formal charter, continues meeting monthly to implement and discuss recommendations made during the 2022 and 2024 workshops, as well as to advance data stewardship to enhance the value and scientific potential of NASA suborbital data.

Appendices

Appendix A: Organizing committee members

Sara Lubkin (ESDIS)

Stephanie Wingo (ADMG)

Megan Buzanowicz (ASDC)

Bruce Wilson (ORNL)

Michele Thornton (ORNL)

Geoffrey Stano (GHRC)

Leigh Sinclair (GHRC)

Jennifer Brennan (ESDIS)

Yaxing Wei (ORNL)

Katherine Saad (NASA HQ)

Appendix B: Workshop registration and attendee metrics

Self-designated registrant status

Self-identified registrant user type

Did you attend the workshop in 2022?

Have you personally worked with airborne/field data?

Participant Science Communities:

Types of Activities Attendees Have Worked On

Summary of Workshop Metrics

Workshop Attendees

- 135 Registered Attendees
- Maximum attendance day 1: 89 attendees
- Maximum attendance day 2: 79 attendees

Appendix C: Examples of workshop feedback

Table C1: Sample of Feedback from Session 1, Recap of 2024 Workshop

Feedback	Notes
DC8 is no longer available, new B777 operating out of NASA Langley Research Center (timeline?)	Getting the word out to the community/stakeholders
Suborbital - why do we love? Calibrate, compliments space obs, drives new questions, motivates and stays with us Opportunity for students and early career	Communication and Outreach
Challenge <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Continue discussions and focus on discovery, usability and SPD-41a will be a priority - forward looking policy Look for new requirements 	Open Science
Mission Tools Suite (MTS) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Satellite underpass planning Strip charts of real time data OGC standards are used - 	Tools and services, collaboration with other orgs, visualizations
Need to be clearer on accomplishments, improvements, the broader dissemination/share progress on goals and achievements with stakeholders. Example. Web Unification effort - visualization, early DAAC selection, etc.	Communication
Challenges: Need for standards across multiple orgs, visualization, data spread out (too many website, hard to grasp scope), not user friendly, complicated, AR datasets	Communication, Outreach, Standards, Tools and Services
Hoping to gain <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Better understanding, perspectives, input What are the needs - highlight of needs Interest of data providers and users 	Communication, collaboration
Public awareness of: Online training using existing tools, need to point to resources. For example ARSET, CASEI, etc.	Communication, training, outreach, know your audience

Table C2: Sample of feedback from Session 3, Groups and Working Groups

Feedback	Notes
Semantics and vocabulary are important - improve GCMD keywords	Metadata
Needs from satellite users to have better access to non-satellite (airborne) data that support cal/val efforts for satellite missions	Tools, search & discovery
Continue to build out resource center with additional material	Outreach
Continue to support open science and figure out how suborbital fits in	Open-Source Science
Address disconnect between DMP content creation and PCS expectations	Standards
Long-term vision: promote awareness and application of NASA's suborbital Earth observations	
Provide end-user feedback to suborbital campaigns (accessibility, data formats, etc.)	Communication, Outreach
Add link to earthdata Pub to resource center	Outreach

Table C3: Sample of feedback from Session 5, Stewardship and Scientist Panel.

Feedback	Notes
Tutorial development with use cases have been very valuable	Continue with tutorials
Jupyter notebooks	Openscapes and similar activities, need to expand/continue
Planning ahead whether satellite and/or airborne & field data to anticipate needs for visualization to support mission	Anticipate early visualization needs
Science team generated tools: analysis and/or visualization -> propagate outward	Openscience i.e. sharing of code
SnowEx hackweeks - getting users involved early working together	Data stewardship, collaborating
Cloud-based data analysis tools to help with data integration	Outreach/education -> science in the cloud -> accelerate adoption/tutorials
Discoverability across agencies, want quality observations (NASA, NOAA, ESA, USGS, etc.)	Discoverability based on search criteria, geophysical parameter
Data organized by investigator	metadata preservation,
Tools for discoverability to scan across multiple campaigns, deployments, etc.	Cross agency/investigation/ discoverability
standards and consistency in metadata and stewardship necessary to enable discovery capacity that responds to user needs	importance of consistency: standard, approach, implementation

Table C4: Sample of Responses from the Registrants Survey.

Career Stage	Have you worked with airborne and field data?	What do you find most challenging regarding the discovery/findability/access/use of NASA airborne and field data?	Feedback pieces to use
Early Career and/or Postdoc	No	The most challenging thing is the use of the information found in the right way to benefit the most people and can provide knowledge about the discovered things to people in every community. until it can bring benefits on a wide scale	Accessibility, how to bring data to the most people, equity - democratization - social justice
Early Career and/or Postdoc	No	I am an economist, I want to learn more on the usage of NASA airborne and field data.	Outreach, communication
Early Career and/or Postdoc	Yes	accessibility of data	accessibility of data can be challenging
Early Career and/or Postdoc	Yes	Specificity of data makes it difficult to co-exist in the same tools as satellite data	aligning airborne & field data with satellite observations is challenging
Late Career	No	I would like to use airborne and field data in conjunction with data from satellite missions, but it is hard to link them together, especially for initial evaluation (e.g., visualization).	finding concurrent data -> tutorials. Flight catalog with orbital overpass. World View visualization
Late Career	No	the data processing part	training and tutorials; higher level products access
Late Career	Yes	narrowing down the vast amounts of data and piecing together what I need from multiple formats	subsetting across multiple inconsistent formats is challenging
Late Career	Yes	Filtering search results when a large number of collections are returned by initial search.	relevant search results and filtering is challenging
Mid Career	Yes	It will be more easy to use the data with the details of description of the dataset	locating dataset descriptions is challenging
Mid Career	Yes	Uncertainties of the measurements seem not clearly described.	locating information on measurement uncertainties is challenging
Student	No	Data size	data access and use
Student	No	Findability and access	findability, accessibility are challenging

Appendix D: Feedback Themes

From within each of the identified feedback categories, the workshop team further elucidated several common themes in participants' feedback. These themes were used to further group the individual feedback items and assess what key actions might be needed to address any challenges. Tables below present examples of sorting themes from feedback items within a category.

Table D1: *Tools and Services Category Feedback: Example items highlighting common themes from visualization tools to improving subsetting capabilities.*

Feedback: Tools & Services
Mission Tools Suite (MTS) Satellite underpass planning Strip charts of real time data OGC standards are used -
Challenges Need visualization
GIS visualization of facility instruments flights
Produce tools and notebooks for visualizing and harmonizing airborne data from multiple campaigns (e.g., IceBridge Portal and IceFlow)
Visualization: Including consideration of flight path vs. instrument swath - Pick a campaign, pick a variable, show all the tracks
initial, quick plotting and visualization of airborne & field data are challenging
visualization, spread out (too many website, hard to grasp scope)
Tools for discoverability to scan across multiple campaigns, deployments, etc.
Be able to merge datasets, creating merge datasets, managing merge datasets generated by science teams
Coincident data: way to feed in aircraft coordinates and time in order to find the corresponding satellite granule that you really want
Aligning airborne & field data with satellite observations is challenging
Making joint tutorials between synergistic airborne/spaceborne datasets hosted by multiple DAACS
Integrating field data into PO.DAAC satellite tools/services: SOTO, HiTIDE
Spatiotemporal subsetting is challenging
Subsetting across multiple inconsistent formats is challenging

Table D2: Search & Discovery Category Feedback: Example items highlighting common themes from improving findability of airborne and field data with specific criteria to being able to perform variable-based searching and filtering.

Feedback: Search & Discovery
Findability, accessibility are challenging
Finding concurrent data -> tutorials. Flight catalog with orbital overpass.
Finding specific airborne/field data product can be challenging
Findability, accessibility are challenging
Searching across (or within?) larger data volumes can be challenging
Relevant search results and filtering is challenging
Variable-based searching is challenging
Would like more opportunity to slice/dice data from CASEI

Appendix E: Resources

- 2024 [Workshop web page](#) (contains workshop recordings)
- 2022 Workshop web page (contains recordings and 2022 report)
- [ADMG web page](https://earthdata.nasa.gov/esds/impact/admg): <https://earthdata.nasa.gov/esds/impact/admg>
- Tools:
 - [CASEI](https://impact.earthdata.nasa.gov/casei/): <https://impact.earthdata.nasa.gov/casei/>
 - [SOOT Power User Interface](https://asdc.larc.nasa.gov/soot/power-user): <https://asdc.larc.nasa.gov/soot/power-user>
 - [Soil Moisture Visualizer](https://airmoss.ornl.gov/visualize/): <https://airmoss.ornl.gov/visualize/>
 - [Airborne Data Visualizer](https://daac.ornl.gov/tools/airborne-data-visualizer-project-list/):
<https://daac.ornl.gov/tools/airborne-data-visualizer-project-list/>
 - [Spatial Data Access Tool](https://webmap.ornl.gov/ogc): <https://webmap.ornl.gov/ogc>
 - [FCX](https://ghrc.earthdata.nasa.gov/fcx/index.html): <https://ghrc.earthdata.nasa.gov/fcx/index.html>
- [ADMG Terms/Definitions](https://earthdata.nasa.gov/esds/impact/admg/admg-definitions): <https://earthdata.nasa.gov/esds/impact/admg/admg-definitions>

AFDRC

Airborne and Field Data Resource Center

Header of the recently created Airborne and Field Data Resource Center, which was created as a result of feedback. AFDRC: <https://www.earthdata.nasa.gov/centers/afdrc>

Inside the Process

From presentation by Steve Olding 5/1/2022

<https://earthdata.nasa.gov/esdis/eso/standards-process>

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Slide from Beth Huffer's presentation highlighting the ESCO Review Process.

ESCO: <https://www.earthdata.nasa.gov/about/esdis/esco>

Appendix F: Acronym List

ABOVE	Arctic-Boreal Vulnerability Experiment
ADMG	Airborne Data Management Group
AFDRC	Airborne and Field Data Resource Center
AFDWG	Airborne and Field Data Working Group
AI/ML	Artificial Intelligence/Machine Learning
API	Application Programming Interface
ARSET	Applied Remote Sensing Training Program
ASDC	Atmospheric Science Data Center
AWS	Amazon Web Services
BioSCape	Biodiversity Survey of the Cape
CASEI	Catalog of Archived Suborbital Earth Science Investigations
CMR	Common Metadata Repository
CryoGARS	Cryosphere Geophysics and Remote Sensing
DAAC	Distributed Active Archive Center
DAPR	Dual-Anonymous Peer Review
DEIA	Diversity, Equity, Inclusion and Accessibility
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EDC	Earthdata Cloud
EO	Earth Observations
ESA	European Space Agency
ESCO	ESDIS Standards Coordination Office
ESDIS	Earth Science Data Information Systems
ESDS	Earth Science Data Systems

ESDSWG	Earth Science Data Systems Working Group
EVS	Earth-Venture Suborbital
FCX	Field Campaign Explorer
FI	Facility Instrument
GCMD	Global Change Master Directory
GDG	Google Developer Group
GHRC	Global Hydrometeorology Resource Center
GIS	Geographic Information Systems
GSFC	Goddard Space Flight Center
HQ	Headquarters
HyTES	Hyperspectral Thermal Emission Spectrometer
IIP	Investigation Implementation Plan
IMPACT	Interagency Implementation and Advanced Concepts Team
IMPACTS	Investigation of Microphysics and Precipitation for Atlantic Coast-Threatening Snowstorms
INCUS	Investigation of Convective Updrafts
JPL	Jet Propulsion Laboratory
LOE	Level of Effort
LVIS	Land, Vegetation, and Ice Sensor
NASA	National Aeronautics and Space Administration
NGEE	Next-Generation Ecosystem Experiments
NOAA	National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration
NSIDC	National Snow and Ice Data Center
O'FAIR	Open, Free, Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
ORNL	Oak Ridge National Laboratory
PCS	Preservation Content Specification

PO DAAC	Physical Oceanography DAAC
RFC	Request for Comment
ROSES	Research Opportunities in Space and Earth Science
S-MODE	Sub-Mesoscale Ocean Dynamics Experiment
SARP	Student Airborne Research Program
SOOT	Sub-Orbital Order Tool
TEMPO	Tropospheric Emissions: Monitoring of Pollution
TOPS	Transform to Open Science
UMM	Unified Metadata Model
U.S.A.	United States of America
USGS	United States Geological Survey